

Effect of some media components and organic additives on callus induction in rice anther culture

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One constraint in rice anther culture is the low frequency of callus induction. Although we can trigger high frequency of callus induction in liquid medium, only a few anthers may respond. We sought to induce a high number of anthers that produce calli by determining the effect of some media components and organic additives — N, mannitol, coconut water, and mashed banana — on callus production.

Taipei 309 anthers at mid-uninucleate to early binucleate development were inoculated in Linbro multiwell plates. Individual anthers were placed in 1.0- × 0.6 cm wells at a plating density of 1 anther/ 0.3 ml medium. They were plated horizontally with the lower surface touching the medium. Cold treatment at 10°C for 8 d followed. Then the plates were kept in darkness at 25°C for 6 wk,

after which we recorded the number of anthers that produced calli. E₁₀ semisolid — a modification of Gamborg's B-5 medium — was used as the base medium in all four experiments.

In the N content experiment, the E₁₀ control had optimum concentration for inducing maximum anther-producing calli (see table). NH₄⁺ was added to E₁₀ medium as 134 mg (NH₄⁺)₂SO₄/litre and NO₃⁻ was added as 2500 mg KNO₃/litre.

Adding mannitol at 1% stimulated the most anthers and induced almost 1.5 times as many calli as the control.

Although not considered as a readily available C source, mannitol may influence the medium's osmotic potential, a critical factor in callus induction.

Coconut water contains myo-inositol, growth regulators, and aminoacids, which can increase callus production.

Adding 10% coconut water produced 1.4 times the calli in the control. Mashed banana increases plantlet formation in immature orchid embryos, but inhibits rice callus induction. *ℒ*

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Treatment	Anthers plated (no.)	Anther-producing calli	
		no.	%
	<i>N</i> ^a		
E ₁₀	149	21	14
E ₁₀ - 0.5 N	149	16	11
E ₁₀ - 1.5 N	149	17	11
E ₁₀ - 2.0 N	149	8	5
	<i>Mannitol</i> ^b		
E ₁₀	168	30	18
E ₁₀ - M ₁	168	43	26
E ₁₀ - M ₂	168	35	21
E ₁₀ - M ₃	168	26	15
	<i>Coconut water</i> ^c		
E ₁₀	185	18	10
E ₁₀ - C ₅	185	16	9
E ₁₀ - C ₁₀	185	25	13
E ₁₀ - C ₁₅	185	17	9
	<i>Mashed banana</i> ^d		
E ₁₀	223	23	10
E ₁₀ - B ₅	223	23	10
E ₁₀ - B ₁₀	223	14	6
E ₁₀ - B ₁₅	223	2	1

^a N concentration (NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻) relative to E₁₀ in the control were 0.5, 1.5, and 2.0 times that of E₁₀. ^b Mannitol concentrations were 0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0% wt/vol. ^c Coconut water concentrations were 0, 5.0, 10.0, and 15.0% vol/vol. ^d Mashed banana concentrations were 0, 5, 10 and 15% wt/vol.

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Rice grain discoloration and its chemical control

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Surveys indicate that rice grain discoloration (also known as glume discoloration, dirty panicle, or pecky rice) commonly occurs in Haryana.

Infected grains are covered with brown-to dark brown lesions. Isolations from the infected grains suggest the primary causal organisms are *Curvularia lunata*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

We studied the control of grain discoloration at HAURRS in 1984. Fungicides edifenphos, zineb, mancozeb, thiophanate-methyl, carbendazim,

Effect of chemical treatment on grain discoloration and yield at Kaul, India.

Treatment	Application rate (%)	Discolored grain ^a (%)	Yield ^a (t/ha)
Edifenphos	0.1	43	7.6
Zineb	0.2	54	7.6
Mancozeb	0.15	51	7.3
Thiophanate-methyl	0.1	55	7.4
Carbendazim	0.2	64	7.4
Captafol	0.2	53	7.5
IBP	0.1	53	7.4
Sevin	0.4	56	7.6
Control	—	63	7.3
CD (0.05)	—	11	ns

^a Mean of 3 replications.

captafol, and IBP and an insecticide, sevin, were sprayed on susceptible Jaya at heading. To increase their efficacy, the chemical solutions were prepared in 0.01% Sel Wet 99 solution. To evaluate results, 20 panicles were randomly collected from each plot at harvest and

examined for diseased seeds. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications.

Only edifenphos and mancozeb gave significant disease control. None of the chemicals significantly increased yield (see table). *ℒ*